

The development of a field service management information system to help companies manage field workers: proposed prototype

This paper is Systematic Literature Review using Barbara Kitchenham methods to collect the research gap to develop FSM apps as proposed prototype

We provided **.ris** file after conducted 3 stage of Barbara Kitchenham methods on attached

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research employs the Rapid Application Development (RAD) methodology, which is particularly suitable for developing prototypes and iterative systems. RAD was chosen for its flexibility and ability to quickly incorporate user feedback, which is crucial when developing novel applications of emerging technologies like digital twins. RAD was selected due to its many benefits, one of which is the ability to create applications based on prototypes. The prototype is designed iteratively, going through specific stages to gather input as needed. Another benefit of developing a system with the RAD technique is that it is a quick procedure with passable outcomes [23]. Our RAD process consisted of four phases:

- Requirements Planning: We defined and proposed an idea by collecting literature information related to the prototype's features.
- Design: We created initial wireframes and user flow diagrams using a UML diagram based on the requirements.
- Construction: The prototype was developed using Figma for a collaborative web/mobile application for interface design, and digital twin functionality was implemented using IoT and AR visualization.
- Cutover: The full implementation was beyond the scope of this prototype study.

DISCUSSION

As technology advances across numerous industries, there is a growing desire for technical solutions that help optimize corporate operations [24]. In this context, we provide a study investigating creative solutions by creating a Field Service Management (FSM) application prototype. This prototype provides an excellent solution for planning and scheduling, asset management, predictive maintenance, customer support, and various other aspects [25]. One notable characteristic is the incorporation of Digital Twin capabilities, which allow for a virtual depiction of physical systems while offering detailed and real-time insights into ongoing operations. This study demonstrates how combining these sophisticated technologies may improve efficiency and effectiveness across various industrial applications [26]. In RAD, the development stage consists of three stages: Requirements Planning, User Design, Construction, and Cutover [27].

A. Requirements Planning

The requirement planning strategy involved preparing an intuitive user interface for real-time tracking, monitoring, and managing field workers and assets. This mobile application allows managers to view the status and performance of their field operations in real-time, resulting in more informed decisions and operational efficiency. The suggested FSM method aims to provide a comprehensive solution that enhances overall field worker management, resulting in better service delivery and customer satisfaction.

B. Design

Fig. 1. Use Case Diagram for Tracktivity

We present our idea as a Use Case, as shown in Fig. 1. Use cases are often utilized in software engineering. They help in design, analysis, testing, verification, and support for specifications [28].

Fig. 2. Class Diagram for Tracktivity

After creating the use case, we create a class diagram, as shown in Fig. 2. This diagram illustrates our proposed solution by capturing the key components, attributes, and interactions.

C. Construction

We later visualized it within a Prototype made in Figma. To effectively plan prototyping techniques for conceptual design, one must be thoroughly aware of the potentialities of the various prototype typologies [29].

Fig. 3. (a) Login, (b) Home Screen (Manager), and (c) Home Screen (Technician)

With the use of mobile phones and their applications, we have entered a digital age where everything is available at our fingertips [30]. When you first run Tracktivity, you will be greeted with a welcoming Splash Screen. It's as if the app greets hello, establishing the tone for the remainder of the workday.

Following that, you will be offered the choice of logging in as a field technician or a field manager based on your role, and the home screen will reflect this.

There are subtle differences based on your selected role on the Schedule page.

Fig. 4. (a) Schedule (Manager) and (b) Schedule (Technician)

There are subtle differences based on your selected role on the Schedule page. The manager can access various features, such as rearranging jobs, editing jobs, and adding a new job to the schedule. Managers can see every upcoming job available to every technician. On the other hand, technicians can only view jobs available to them.

Fig. 5. (a) Job List (Manager) and (b) Job List (Technician)

The same goes for the Job List page, where managers can edit and add jobs. The page is simple: It shows lists of jobs filtered by specific conditions. Technicians can access only their jobs, while managers can see everything. You can tap on a specific job to view its details. Technicians have two main additions: a task list feature and a contact manager feature.

Fig. 6. (a) Chat (Technician) and (b) Task List

These are the chat and task list features that will show after you select the specific icon of that task. Chat lets you communicate with others within the built-in chat system inside Tracktivity. They can talk to other managers or discuss with technicians who are presently working on a job. A Task List will show you every task that needs to be done for that specific job that has been selected.

(a) (b)

Fig. 7. (a) Collaboration and (b) Knowledge Base

Near-eye displays and tracking technologies are crucial for VR/AR applications, addressing ergonomics, comfort, visual quality, and natural interaction challenges while addressing unresolved research questions [31]. The applications used in AR are Healthcare, Education, Retail, Military, Industrial and manufacturing, Engineering, Marketing, advertising, etc. [32], [33]. Currently, we are using this application for training and educational purposes. Tracktivity allows users to show real-time data and information using the augmented reality camera in the Collaboration feature. Not just a simple AR camera, With the help of Digital Twin, it will create a digital replica of the physical environment, allowing users to interact with and view live data as if they were navigating within a parallel digital world, offering insights and functionalities that mirror the real-world environment in real-time.

Tracktivity also offers a real-time, step-by-step manual through the Knowledge-Based feature. This feature utilizes the advanced capabilities of Digital Twin technology. Its idea is to create a digital replica of the asset, offering an in-depth interactive manual to help technicians complete their tasks.

(a) (b)

Fig. 8. (a) Predictive Analysis and (b) Performance Monitoring

Field service management software frequently requires many forms of maintenance, including reactive, preventive, and predictive. Reactive maintenance has been used for a long time and is an essential component [34]. Tracktivity's Predictive Analysis feature allows managers to track and predict the maintenance of a specific asset. They can review the historical data for each piece of equipment. Predictive maintenance is like Historical Equipment Data Analysis in that it provides management with information about how long each piece of equipment should last between maintenance

needs. Tracktivity will also track each technician based on their performance. Managers can see all technician performance data on the Performance Monitoring page.

Introducing the "Journey" feature in Tracktivity, your personal navigator for monitoring technician activity and completed jobs in real-time using Digital Twin. By clicking the Performance Monitoring icon on the manager home page. In Track Technician Location, the manager can see the technician's last location. Not only are Journey managers informed about where their technicians are located, but it also provides detailed insights into the jobs they have completed. It is like having a digital log of their workday, filled with timestamps and job-related information.

D. Cutover

In this project, which is a proposed prototype rather than a complete application, the cutover phase is viewed as a crucial stage in the eventual shift from development to production. Since this paper focuses on a conceptual proposal and prototype, the cutover phase is described as a future plan rather than a completed action.

Fig. 9. (a) Journey and 8(b) Last Location